

Masked priming under the Bayesian microscope: Exploring the integration of local elements into global shape through Bayesian model comparison.

Mikel Jimenez¹, Antonio Prieto², Pablo Gómez³, José Antonio Hinojosa^{4,5,6} and Pedro R. Montoro²

¹ Department of Psychology, University of Durham, Durham, United Kingdom

² Departamento de Psicología Básica I, UNED, Spain

³ California State University San Bernardino, Palm Desert Campus, USA

⁴ Facultad de Lenguas y Educación, Universidad de Nebrija, Madrid, Spain

⁵ Instituto Pluridisciplinar, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain

⁶ Departamento de Psicología Experimental, Procesos Psicológicos y Logopedia, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain

Corresponding authors:

Mikel Jimenez
Department of Psychology
Durham University
Upper Mountjoy, South Rd, Durham DH1 3LE
E-mail: mikel.jimenez@durham.ac.uk

Antonio Prieto
Departamento de Psicología Básica I
UNED
C. de Juan del Rosal, 10, 28040 Madrid, Spain
E-mail: antonioprieto@psi.uned.es

Keywords: Awareness; Unconscious perception; Priming; Bayesian inference; Perceptual organization; Shape perception; Visual masking

Abstract

To investigate whether local elements are grouped into global shapes in the absence of awareness, we introduced two different masked priming designs (e.g., the classic dissociation paradigm and a trial-wise probe and prime discrimination task) and collected both objective (i.e., performance based) and subjective (using the perceptual awareness scale [PAS]) awareness measures. Prime visibility was manipulated using three different prime-mask stimulus onset asynchronies (SOAs) and an unmasked condition. Our results showed that assessing prime visibility trial-wise heavily interfered with masked priming producing no prime facilitation effects. The implementation of Bayesian regression models, which predict priming effects for participants whose awareness levels are at chance level, provided strong evidence in favor of the hypothesis that local elements group into global shape in the absence of awareness for SOAs longer than 50 ms, suggesting that prime-mask SOA is a crucial factor in the processing of the global shape without awareness.

1. Introduction

We perceive a coherent world of individual objects arranged into meaningful scenes, an organized visual image that emerges from an ambiguous two-dimensional retinal input composed of different intensities and wavelengths of light. The visual aggregation of discrete elements into global structured patterns occurs across several perceptual stages (Marr, 1982; Palmer, 1999), where different perceptual organization operations (e.g., contour processing, grouping operations, figure-ground segmentation or modal/amodal completions) take place at several processing levels (Behrmann & Kimchi, 2003; Kimchi, 1998, 2000; see Wagemans et al., 2012, for a review). This complex visual processing contrasts with the seemingly effortless phenomenological visual experience of our environment, which seems to be available to us immediately in a perceptually organized fashion. Classic cognitive theories of visual processing assume that at least some basic perceptual grouping operations occur preattentively, generating ‘proto-objects’ for the in-depth analysis of subsequent attentive processes (Kahneman & Henik, 1981; Neisser, 1967; Treisman, 1982, 1985). Indeed, many studies have supported that visual grouping can occur outside the focus of selective attention (Chan & Chua, 2003; Driver et al., 2001; Kimchi & Razpurker-Apfeld, 2004; Lamy et al., 2006; Mitroff & Scholl, 2005; Moore & Egeth, 1997; Rashal et al., 2017; Russell & Driver, 2005; Vandenbroucke et al., 2012).

The fact that perceptual grouping might occur for unattended stimuli, however, would not imply that those stimuli (and hence the grouping processes behind them) are processed in the complete absence of an observer’s awareness¹. Thus, more recent studies have explored whether visual awareness is a critical factor in perceptual organization. Montoro et al. (2014) showed that masked arrays of local elements could be grouped together by proximity and similarity principles in the absence of participants’ awareness. Kimchi et al. (2018) found similar results for luminance similarity and connectedness when the stimulus was rendered invisible using visual masking, yet they did not observe unconscious perceptual grouping when they used continuous flash suppression (CFS; Breitmeyer, 2015), a technique that allows less processing of the suppressed visual information (e.g., Breitmeyer, 2015; Moors et al., 2017). One aspect of perceptual

¹ Note that the relation between attention and awareness is an intense topic of debate. Evidence of double dissociations between attention and consciousness (Koch & Tsuchiya, 2007) cast doubt on the long-held view of attention as a gateway to consciousness (Chica & Bartolomeo, 2013). For the interested reader, we recommend the articles cited above together with the opinion article by Cohen et al. (2012) and the review by Marchetti (2012).

organization that remains less well understood is whether the integration of local elements into global shapes — either in hierarchical or non-hierarchical visual arrays — occurs in the absence of awareness. A classic example of a hierarchical visual array is the global/local paradigm originally introduced by Navon (1977), where large letters (global level) made up of small letters (local level) are presented under globally or locally directed attentional conditions (see Kimchi, 2015, for a review). In a non-hierarchical visual array, the global representation is composed of local elements that are neutral to (i.e., do not interfere with) the perception of the global level (and vice versa). Koivisto and Revonsuo (2004) used a masked priming paradigm and interocular suppression to explore whether the global or the local level of hierarchical letters were processed in the absence of awareness of the primes. Results showed that only global primes facilitated the identification of the target letter, suggesting a priority for global processing already at a non-conscious level, in line with the hypothesis that perceptual processing of complex objects proceeds from the global structure to the analysis of the local elements (Navon, 1977, 1981). However, this occurred only when attention was selectively focused on, or biased to, the global level. Using metacontrast masking and non-hierarchical arrays, Breitmeyer et al. (2005) found that non-hierarchical square or diamond primes defined only by the sides of the geometric shapes (with no corner information) would not produce priming effects when rendered invisible with metacontrast masking, yet primes defined only by their corners would subliminally prime subsequent targets (whole square or diamonds). Schwarzkopf and Rees (2011) used counter-phase contrast flickering and presented participants with shape primes defined by position (small dots, which included corner information) or orientation (small, oriented Gabor elements, with no corner information) cues, which might generate square or diamond shapes. When the primes were rendered invisible, position-defined primes produced only within-cue priming (suggesting that the local features produced the effect), whereas orientation-defined primes showed only cross-cue priming, which would suggest that the integration of the local elements into a global shape was taking place. When controlling for retinotopic effects, no priming effects were found for any of the invisible primes. More recently, Jimenez et al. (2017) used a visual masking design and non-hierarchical primes consisting of local *pacmen* that could group into global square and diamond shapes. They found significant response priming effects for the global shape of the prime when the prime-mask SOA (stimulus onset asynchrony) was 53 ms, but not when it was 27 ms, suggesting that prime duration might be a crucial factor in the construction of the global shape in the absence of awareness.

Overall, the current evidence on the integration of local elements into global shapes in the absence of awareness is mixed, and there are still important aspects that need to be taken into further consideration. A fundamental observation is that results from different studies may differ depending on the type of stimuli used and the method introduced to render them invisible. Regarding the latter, it is well known that some techniques (e.g., visual masking) allow further processing of stimulus information than others (suppression techniques, such as continuous flash suppression), which seem to disrupt stimulus information at very early stages of visual processing (see Breitmeyer, 2015, for a review). Within unconscious priming research, visual masking should be the preferred technique, because it renders the stimulus invisible while not completely suppressing stimulus information from further processing within the visual system. Additionally, visual masking resembles the stimulus conditions that occur in real environments everyday: several stimuli following each other in a relative quick succession (Kim & Blake, 2005). In relation to the nature of the stimuli, because observed results are affected by hierarchical vs non-hierarchical arrays and by retinotopic effects, studies exploring the global integration of local elements into global shapes should account and control for these two effects. Finally, the specific method by which prime visibility is assessed in the studies that aim to explore perceptual operations under the threshold of awareness should also be taken into account.

Indeed, most of the studies on the global integration of local elements (e.g., Breitmeyer et al., 2005; Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2004; Jimenez et al., 2017; Montoro et al., 2014) have employed the classic dissociation paradigm (Reingold & Merikle, 1988) aimed to show differences between a performance measure and an awareness measure on the same stimuli. Following this logic, participants in a typical masked priming study perform two different tasks: a forced-choice reaction time (RT) task on the identity of the probe stimulus (i.e., the priming task, a measure of performance), immediately followed by a forced-choice prime discrimination task aimed to provide an objective index of prime visibility (i.e., the prime visibility task, a measure of awareness). If participants' performance is at chance-level in the prime discrimination task, and significant prime effects are found in the masked priming task, it is concluded that the prime's relevant information is processed by the visual system in the absence of awareness. Since the visibility of the primes is assessed through participants' ability to discriminate the prime based on objective accuracy levels, this is thought to reflect an *objective* (yet indirect) measurement of awareness (Persuh, 2018). This method has been criticized because aggregated awareness (e.g.,

mean awareness level of the whole sample) might not be at strict chance level (Rouder et al., 2007). Also, since the visibility of the prime is not assessed on a trial-by-trial basis but rather in a different experimental block, the prime could be (minimally) visible in some (or many) trials during the priming task. To overcome the first problem, post hoc data selection has been used in many studies (see Shanks, 2017, for a review), where data from participants whose awareness score is below some specific cut-off (typically chance-level in the prime visibility task) are analyzed separately. For this subset of “unaware participants”, their mean score on the performance measure is then calculated. If significant priming effects are found for this subset of participants, the occurrence of true unconscious perception is concluded. However, this solution is controversial, and its use has been highly discouraged (Rothkirch et al., 2022; Shanks, 2017; but see Sklar et al., 2021, for an alternative account) as it might produce a *regression to the mean*. This statistical phenomenon refers to the fact that selecting a subsample of participants based on their awareness and using the selected awareness values to compute mean awareness in this sub-group of participants amounts to “double-dipping” (i.e., using the same measure twice), which introduces a bias because the measurement error is no longer randomly sampled amongst the sub-group (Rothkirch et al., 2022). One proposed way for avoiding these statistical problems is to use the regression-based method proposed by Greenwald et al. (1995). Within this approach, the *unconscious* priming effect is predicted in a linear regression model from prime awareness values that are centered (by subtracting the chance level from the actual performance values) so that a value of zero indicates no awareness of the prime. The regression intercept represents the predicted priming effect for a hypothetical participant with the awareness performance at chance level in a forced-choice measure. However, several studies showed that the Greenwald regression is a biased estimate of the unconscious effect (e.g., Doshier, 1998; Klauer et al., 1998; Sand & Nilsson, 2016), as it produces an overestimation of the intercept value. In order to overcome this problem, Goldstein et al. (2022) recently proposed a new solution that implements a Bayesian generative model for estimating the intercept in a regression model while accounting for the error in the awareness and effect measurements.

Alternatively, a different approach to assess participants’ awareness of the primes is to gather participants’ *subjective* reports of their visual experience on each trial of the main task by means of an “online” awareness measure (e.g., Van den Bussche et al., 2013). The appeal of subjective measures lies in the fact that introspective reports, unlike objective measures, are more directly

related to participants' conscious visual perception (Dehaene and Naccache, 2001; Merikle et al., 2001; Persuh, 2018). Based on this trial-by-trial awareness assessment, the unconscious and the conscious trials can be analysed separately without a need to conduct a post hoc test of prime visibility. Following this approach, Sabary et al. (2020) recently examined whether the integration of local elements into a global shape requires visual awareness, using a masked priming paradigm and gathering participants' reports on subjective online visibility of the primes on a trial-by-trial basis using the Perceptual Awareness Scale (PAS, Ramsøy & Overgaard, 2004). This scale includes the visibility categories of "no perception", "brief glimpse", "almost clear perception" and "clear perception". The authors introduced two different prime conditions (either hierarchical patterns composed of many relatively small elements or composed of a few relatively large elements). Participants responded to either the global shape (global block) or the shape of their local elements (local block) in a forced-choice RT task, results showing unconscious (i.e., "no perception reports") priming effects only by the local elements. The authors thus concluded that when local elements are represented in the absence of visual awareness, regardless of their number and relative size, visual awareness is essential for grouping local elements into a global shape. Critically, the authors did not conduct an objective discrimination measure of the global and local forms of the primes.

The use of subjective awareness reports in consciousness research, however, is not devoid of experimental challenges. Indeed, subjective reports of awareness are frequently criticized because they are susceptible to response biases (e.g., Erdelyi, 1974; Eriksen, 1960; Holender, 1986; Shanks & St. John, 1994) and criterion confounds (Bachmann, 2015; Kahneman, 1968; Jimenez et al., 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021; Sackur, 2013). The importance of criterion confounds was already highlighted by Kahneman (1968) more than fifty years ago, where he reflected on how the question of criterion content seems to concern with phenomenology, and "request a fuller description of the code that the subject uses in mapping his private experience onto responses to the experimenter's questions" (p. 410). In the case of PAS, participants' criterion to report "no perception" or "brief glimpse", for example, is influenced by how conservative they are in reporting their subjective experience (Spener, 2020; Tunney & Shanks, 2003). In other words, a very conservative criterion might bias participants' reports towards "no perception" even when the prime is minimally perceived, and, conversely, a less conservative criterion could bias participants' reports towards "brief glimpse" category. In addition, the presentation of the primes "sandwiched" between two

masks – all three stimuli presented in rapid succession –, might produce a further bias towards “brief glimpse” reports if participants identify this brief “flash” of stimuli as something perceived. Not least, the use of the subjective awareness scale might also produce criterion-shift related problems when different tasks are introduced within the same experimental design yet no explicit instructions on the use of the awareness scale are provided (see Jimenez et al, 2020, for a review). In Sabary et al.’s study, for example, the criterion used for reporting awareness levels might differ between observers and/or within observers in the two blocks of the priming task (i.e., local vs. global blocks). Since no explicit instructions are provided on the use of the PAS, participants’ criterion may shift from reporting the (absence, brief, or almost/clear) perception of the local elements in both the local and global blocks to reporting the perception of the global shape, or vice versa, in any of the two blocks or even on a trial-to-trial basis. This criterion confound might lead to trials in the global block where participants report a “brief glimpse” of the prime exclusively based on the (marginal) perception of an individual local element without being aware of the global shape of the prime per se, thus influencing the reliability of subsequent priming effects.

A further issue when introducing online PAS reports in a response priming paradigm is that it *de facto* converts the task into a dual-task paradigm, hence dividing participants’ attention between the assessment of prime visibility and the response to the probe, and most likely influencing the results in the forced-choice reaction task to the probe identity. Indeed, this dual-task effect seems to be manifested as longer RTs in Sabary et al.’s (2020) when compared to previous studies, which did not use an online measure of awareness (Breitmeyer et al., 2005; Jimenez et al., 2017; Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2004; Montoro et al., 2014; Schwarzkopf & Rees, 2011). Considering that in a response priming task a speeded response to probe identity is required from participants, this attentional diversion and subsequent increase in RTs due to the introduction of the online visibility measure may influence the facilitation (congruency) effect of the primes, possibly weakening prime-related activation and stimulus-response links between prime and probe (e.g., Ansorge et al., 2010; Avneon & Lamy, 2018; Kinoshita & Hunt, 2008). Of note, a further issue in Sabary et al.’s (2021) study is the introduction of a limited number of probes (only two, thus reducing the prime-probe responses to one per condition), which might have produced an item-based priming effect. A possible consequence of this one-to-one assignment of probes and responses might be that participants no longer respond to the category of the prime but process each prime as a unique and particular item. In contrast, several previous masked priming studies have introduced a wider

variety of targets to force participants to base their response on a more general visual category of the stimuli (like *horizontality* and *verticality*; Montoro et al., 2014; or *shape* [square vs. diamond] *likeness*, Jimenez et al., 2017), which might affect the global facilitation of the primes.

In order to address all the concerns mentioned above, in the present study we will expand Sabary et al.'s paradigm to explore whether global shape is constructed in the absence of visual awareness. With this in mind, we will conduct four experiments focused on the global integration of local elements. In all four experiments, global shape arrays (squares or diamonds) made of local elements (triangles and crosses; neutral to the perception of the global form) will be presented as primes in a response priming paradigm. All four experiments will include three different tasks: a classic masked priming paradigm (e.g., the single-task priming block), where participants will give speeded responses to probe identity while ignoring the masked primes; a second masked priming task (e.g., the dual-task priming block) in which, following Sabary et al., prime visibility will be gathered "online" using the PAS scale; and a third task, consisting both of a forced-choice prime discrimination task designed to obtain an objective index (i.e., d') of prime visibility and a subjective awareness measure of the primes (the PAS scale). Importantly, participants will be instructed to inform their subjective experience of the global shape avoiding any report on their subjective visibility of the local elements, to exclude any criterion shift in the use of the PAS (see Michel, 2022, for a similar account). The introduction of three different tasks will allow us to (i) implement both a linear mixed model and a Bayesian regression model (Goldstein, 2022), that allows for an estimation of the intercept (e.g., the priming effect) while accounting for the error in the awareness and effect measurements, (ii) explore whether the introduction of online measures of awareness affects priming effects, by comparing prime facilitation between the single-task and dual-task priming blocks, and (iii) explicitly explore the relation between objective awareness performance and subjective awareness reports using a common sensitivity measure (d') of stimulus visibility. A wider set of probe stimuli with different physical attributes will be introduced in order to force participants to base their responses on the activation of a particular visual category (shape likeness), and therefore reinforce the connection between primes and probes as global stimuli (e.g., category-based as opposed to item-based). The issue of whether prime duration is a crucial factor in the construction of the global shape in the absence of awareness will be carefully considered. Whereas in Sabary et al.'s experiment only one SOA between prime and mask was used (i.e., 40 ms prime duration), here we will use two longer SOAs of 53 ms (Experiment 2) and 67 ms

(Experiment 3), together with a baseline SOA of 40 ms (Exp. 1), as previous significant priming of the global configuration was found for a longer SOA of 53 ms (Jimenez et al., 2017). To confirm that our priming design can produce reliable priming effects, an unmasked condition (Experiment 4) will also be introduced. Retinotopic effects will be controlled across experiments by presenting prime and probes of different fixed sizes.

Overall, our hypotheses are divided according to the different experimental manipulations introduced in this study. In relation to the online measure of awareness manipulation, we expect faster RTs in the single-task priming block compared to the dual-task priming block across all experiments. Assuming that the attentional diversion (and subsequent increase in RTs) in the dual-task priming block affects the facilitation (congruency) effect of the primes, we expect a different pattern of priming effects in the single-task and dual-task priming blocks, with those effects being more reliable in the single-task block across experiments. If prime duration is a critical factor in the construction of global shape from local elements, we expect significant priming effects of the global structure for the longer SOAs of 53 ms and/or 67 ms but not for the shorter SOA of 40 ms. The introduction of Bayesian analyses and generative regression models (Goldstein et al., 2022; Wagenmakers et al., 2018) will complement the evidence provided by the linear mixed models and will allow us to evaluate the results in favor of -or against- the null hypotheses across the different experiments.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

The different samples of participants in each experiment were recruited from the population of undergraduate Psychology students at UNED, aged between 18 and 55 years. All of them reported normal or corrected-to-normal vision and received course credits for their participation. The experiment was conducted with the understanding and written consent of each participant, in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and accepted by the local ethics committee. The sample size for each of the experiments was calculated based on two different factors: the fact that a minimal number of observations should be obtained as a floor, and the need to optimize the resources beyond that floor level. Hence, we did not implement a prospective sample size calculation but, instead, employed a mixed sampling stopping rule (Rouder, 2014; Schönbrodt et al., 2017) based on both a minimum number of observations (participants) and the cumulative

evidence obtained in favor or against the null hypothesis. Specifically, and following Brysbaert and Stevens (2018), a minimum of 20 participants per experiment would be tested, which corresponds to 2560 observations per condition. Following the procedure employed by Matzke et al. (2015), the total number of participants in each experiment was calculated by monitoring the Bayes factor (BF) values in the regression analysis (Goldstein et al., 2022) at the end of each experimental day once the minimum sample size of 20 participants was reached. The evidence for a null model (intercept = 0) was compared to the evidence of a model with intercept $\neq 0$ and the data collection stopped when the comparison reflects “substantial” evidence (e.g., when the data suggests one of the hypotheses is three times more likely than the other, for H_0 , $BF_{01} \geq 3$; and for H_1 , $BF_{01} \leq 1/3$) in favor of any of the two models (see Jeffreys, 1998 for a classification scheme for the Bayes factor). Data collection would, in any case, stop once 100 participants were reached in each of the masked priming experiments (e.g., Exp. 1, 2, & 3). For the unmasked priming (Exp. 4), where clear priming effects were expected, the maximum number of participants was set to 40. The sample of participants did not overlap between experiments (i.e., different groups of participants took part in the different experiments included in the study).

2.2 Apparatus

The stimuli were displayed on a 19-in. LCD–LED Samsung 943N color monitor with a 75-Hz refresh rate, a 5:4 aspect ratio, and a resolution of 1280 x 1024 controlled by a computer running E-Prime 3.0 software (Psychology Software Tools, 1996–2018). The viewing distance was approximately 57 cm. Participants provided their responses by means of a keyboard and a mouse connected to the computer. The testing room was dimly lit.

2.3 Stimuli

All the stimuli were displayed at the center of the screen on a gray background (RGB: 70, 70, 70; 3.3 cd/m²). In all the experiments, four different primes could be presented, two global squares or two global diamonds, made up of twelve local x-shape crosses or triangles (see Figure 1a). The side of the diamond subtended 6° and the side of the square 5°. Each individual x-cross element and each individual triangle subtended 1.7° x 1.7°. The contours of the elements were 3 pixels wide. Twelve square or diamond-shaped probes with different visual features were randomly introduced as probes (see Figure 1b). All the probes in the four experiments were smaller than

primes to avoid retinotopic effects. Specifically, the square probes subtended $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$ and the triangle probes subtended $4^\circ \times 4^\circ$, their shade being light gray (RGB: 190, 190, 190; 33 cd/m²).

The forward and backward masks were the same as those used by Sabary et al. (2021; see Figure 1c). They consisted of 100 gray background color (RGB: 70, 70, 70; 3.3 cd/m²) and light gray (RGB: 190, 190, 190; 33 cd/m²) lines randomly placed inside a square area subtending $7.5^\circ \times 7.5^\circ$. Background color lines were superimposed over light gray color lines in order to create different noise (e.g., line cuts) patterns. Each line subtended between 1° and 1.5° visual angle in length and 4 pixels in width. The orientations of the lines were random, yet lines of 45° orientation and its multiplications were excluded to avoid potential response facilitation by the local elements of the mask. During the experiment, each mask was randomly chosen from a pool of 50 masks and appeared just once in each trial.

Figure 1. Stimuli used in the four different experiments. (a) Prime stimuli for all the experiments. (b) Probe stimuli for all the experiments. (c) Examples of mask stimuli.

2.4. Procedure and design

The four experiments of the present study were independent of each other and, consequently, different samples of participants were recruited for each experiment. Each experiment consisted of three sequential tasks, a single-task priming block, a dual-task priming block, and a prime visibility block (see Figures 2 and 3). The participants recruited for each experiment performed the three tasks sequentially. The sequence of events for a trial in Experiments 1, 2 & 3 (masked primes) is depicted in Figure 2. Each experimental session started with either the single-task

priming block or the dual-task priming block, counterbalanced across participants. Lastly, participants performed the prime visibility block². In the single and dual-task priming blocks, each trial started with a fixation mark ($1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ light grey cross: RGB 210, 210, 210; 49 cd/m²) displayed at the center of the screen for 1000 ms. Then, a forward mask pattern was presented for 100 ms, followed by a prime that was displayed for 40 ms in all the experiments. In Experiment 1, a backward mask pattern was presented for 67 ms immediately after the prime. In Experiments 2 and 3, a blank inter stimulus (ISI) screen was displayed for 13 ms (Exp. 2) or 27 ms (Exp. 3) after the prime; afterwards, the backward mask pattern was presented for 53 ms (Exp. 2) or 40 ms (Exp. 3), in order to maintain a constant 107 ms prime-target SOA across experiments. Finally, in all the experiments, the probe remained on the screen until response or a maximum of 2000 ms after probe onset. The sequence of events for a trial in Experiment 4 (unmasked primes) is depicted in Figure 3. Here, the prime duration was the same as previous experiments (i.e., 40 ms), a blank display was presented for 67 ms (in order to keep a constant 107 ms prime-target SOA across experiments) but no forward or backward mask followed the prime. In all experiments, participants discriminated between the probes (square or diamond) by pressing one of two response buttons of the numeric keypad on the right of the keyboard (number 1 or 2, respectively) with their middle and index fingers of the right hand as fast as possible but avoiding making mistakes. In the single-task priming block, participants were informed about the presentation of the masked primes, but they were told that they are task-irrelevant, and they needed to ignore them. The probe was followed by an intertrial blank screen for 800 ms. In the dual-task priming block, the trial sequence was identical to the single-task priming block yet after participants discriminated between the two possible probes, a question mark was displayed on the screen prompting the participants to provide a subjective report of prime visibility by means of PAS scale ranging from 1 to 4 (1 = No perception, 2 = Weak perception, 3 = Almost Clear perception and 4 = Clear perception) by pressing the “1”, “2”, “3”, or “4” numerical key on the top of the keyboard with the left hand. Participants were explicitly informed that the four categories of the PAS scale referred exclusively to the perception of the global shape of the prime and not the visibility of the local elements that compose the primes. The specific instructions concerning the PAS were: (1) ‘No perception’:

² The prime visibility block will be always performed after the two priming blocks to avoid the underestimation of prime awareness due to possible increases in prime visibility (e.g., increase in light adaptation) during the task (Purcell et al., 1983; Timmermans & Cleeremans, 2015).

There is no subjective experience of the stimulus; (2) ‘Weak perception’: A feeling that some global figure has been shown although this could not be identified, (3) ‘Almost clear perception’: Global shape perceived with some degree of uncertainty. A feeling of almost being certain about one’s answer; (4) ‘Clear experience’: An experience of clearly seeing the global shape. Complete certainty about one’s answer.

In the prime visibility block, participants performed a forced-choice prime discrimination task and they reported their subjective visibility of the prime on the PAS scale afterwards. For this task, the sequence of events was identical to the single-task priming block with the following exceptions: (1) the probe stimuli was not be displayed, (2) after the second mask offset, two response options (“Square” and “Diamond”) were displayed on the center of the screen until participants provide a mouse response and, (3) immediately after, a new screen showed the four labels of the PAS scale where participants provided a judgment of prime visibility scale. The trials in this task were self-administered to ensure that participants were as ready as possible to discriminate the masked prime. Participants were instructed to try to be as accurate as possible and to guess on trials in which they could not identify the primes.

Figure 2. Sequence of events in each block of the experiments 1, 2 and 3.

Table 1. Variable display durations and prime-target SOA (all in ms) across experiments

Experiment	Variable display durations		Prime-target SOA
	ISI	Backward mask	
1	0	67	107
2	13	53	107
3	27	40	107

Each task consisted of 288 experimental trials, including 32 catch trials in which no prime was presented, and were preceded by 24 practice trials (single-task and dual-task priming blocks) or 12 practice trials (prime visibility block). Participants were unaware of the inclusion of catch trials. During the practice trials of the single-task and dual-task priming blocks, feedback was provided only for the practice trials. No feedback was provided in the prime visibility block. There were two breaks within each task and two further breaks between the task, in order to avoid fatigue effects, and during which participants were instructed regarding their task in the next phase. The single task lasted around 20 minutes, the dual-task around 30 minutes, whereas the discrimination block around 20 minutes. In total, including the two between-task breaks and the two within-task breaks, the whole experimental session did not last longer than 90 minutes.

Figure 3. Sequence of events in each block of Experiment 4.

2.5. Data analyses

The Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression method (Goldstein et al., 2022; Greenwald et al., 1995) was performed using RStudio (Version 2022-02-03-492, RStudio, 2022, based on the R programming language Version 4.2.0, R Core Team, 2022, or higher) using the rjags package (Plummer et al., 2006). All the remaining Bayesian tests were performed using JASP statistical software (version 0.16.4, www.jasp-stats.org)³. Trials with RTs more than 2 standard deviations (*SD*) from condition mean for each participant did not enter the analyses. In addition, participants with accuracy levels lower than 75% or more than 10% “clear

³ Repeated measures Bayesian tests were planned to be conducted in RStudio using the BayesFactor (Morey & Rouder, 2022) package. However, BayesFactor computes the repeated measures ANOVA differently than JASP. Both in JASP and in the classical frequentist ANOVAs, the full model contains random slopes for all but the highest order repeated-measures interaction. The BayesFactor repeated measures ANOVA does not include these random slopes (see van den Bergh et al., 2022, for a discussion). For the sake of consistency and comparability, Bayesian tests were therefore conducted using JASP, with a default scale parameter of 0.707 for a Cauchy prior centered on zero.

perception” reports for catch trials were excluded from the analyses. All the analyses detailed in this section were conducted independently for the data gathered in each of the four experiments (but see footnote 4).

The hypothesis that local elements group into global shapes in the absence of visual awareness was explored separately for the single-task priming block and the dual-task priming blocks. The data from the single-task priming block was analyzed following two complementary approaches: the classical dissociation paradigm (Reingold & Merikle, 1988) combined with Bayesian tests, and the newly proposed Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression method (Goldstein et al., 2022).

In the first case, RT data from the single-task priming block was sent to a Bayesian *t*-test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials, for which the Bayes Factor would provide evidence in favor or against a priming effect by the masked primes. To explore whether the masked primes were processed without participant’s awareness, prime discrimination responses from the prime visibility task were transformed into a sensibility measure (d'_{obj}) to produce an objective index of prime visibility. Bayesian *t*-tests were calculated to understand the degree to which the evidence supported (or precludes) chance-level ($d'=0$) prime discrimination of the primes.

In the second analysis, priming effects in the single-task priming block of Experiments 1, 2, & 3 (masked design⁴) were analyzed by implementing a Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression method (Goldstein et al., 2022; Greenwald et al., 1995). Priming scores were predicted from centered awareness scores, with the regression intercept representing the predicted effect for a given participant whose awareness level in the objective task is at chance level. To avoid the overestimation of the intercept due to the regression attenuation (see Goldstein et al., 2022 and Spearman, 1904 for a thorough description), the Bayesian generative modeling approach suggested by Goldstein et al. (2022) was employed, which allows for an unbiased intercept estimation. This method approximates a posterior distribution for the intercept (and 95% credible interval) and a Bayes Factor (BF) comparing the evidence for a null model (intercept = 0) to the evidence of a model in which the intercept $\neq 0$ ⁵.

⁴ Note that implementing the regression method on Experiment 4 would be meaningless, since we expect primes to be partially or clearly visible as the result of removing the masking from the design.

⁵ The process takes place along three different stages: First, the awareness score and its uncertainty for each participant is calculated by specifying a generative model including two subpopulations of nonconscious

RT data from the dual-task priming block was planned to be sent to a 2 x 4 repeated measures Bayesian ANOVA with Congruency (Congruent vs. Incongruent) and PAS (1: No perception; 2: Weak perception; 3: Almost clear perception, and 4: Clear perception) as factors. However, due to the marginal use of PAS3 and PAS4 across experiments (see Results section), only a very small subset of participants would enter the analysis after the listwise deletion of participants with missing values, hence producing no meaningful statistical output. Therefore, evidence supporting the hypothesis that local elements group into global shapes in the absence of visual awareness was gathered by exploring congruency (priming) effects at the PAS1 (no perception) category of the subjective awareness scale⁶.

The hypothesis that RTs increase during the dual-task priming block compared to the single-task priming block was explored by submitting RTs from the two different priming blocks (all trials in the single and dual-task) to a 2 x 2 Bayesian repeated-measures ANOVA with Block (single-task, dual-task) and Congruency (congruent, incongruent) as within-subjects factors. Bayesian Model Averaging (Wagenmakers et al., 2018; Haldane, 1932; Hoeting, Madigan, Raftery, & Volinsky, 1999) was computed across matched models to compare models that contain a specific effect to equivalent models without the effect. Bayesian analysis allowed us to quantify the evidence in favor of the predicted effect while comparing two models: a null model where no differences

(expected value = 0.5) and partially aware participants (expected values ranging from 0.5 to 1). Then, the probability of each participant to belong to one of the two populations and the true awareness score of each participant given their membership to one of the subgroups is estimated (see Goldstein et al., 2022, for specific details on this calculation). This determines whether a participant's true score (θ_i) is drawn from the masked subgroup or the partially aware subgroup. Second, the true behavioral effect (δ_i) and its uncertainty are calculated for each participant. Each response latency is generated from one of two normal distributions of log-transformed RT (RTs are log-transformed to ensure that the distribution of RTs approaches a normal distribution, and thus the normality assumption is satisfied), one for congruent trials and the other for incongruent trials. Then the model estimates the difference between congruent and incongruent distributions to obtain the parameter of interest (δ_i), which is the RT behavioral effect for each participant. Third, the regression coefficients concerning the estimated awareness score and the behavioral effect are estimated, using uncertainty to correct for measurement error. The model uses the output of the two preceding steps to produce corrected regression coefficients and provide unbiased estimates of the true relation between the awareness and effect values (Goldstein et al., 2022; Matzke et al., 2017). Finally, the model derives the centered intercept of the regression model, predicting the true behavioral effect for a true awareness score indicating no awareness.

⁶ The evidence provided by the Bayesian tests in both the single-task and dual-task priming block was complemented with conventional frequentist tests and is presented as Supplementary material (see Supplementary materials for a description of the different analyses).

between single and dual task designs exists, and an alternative model that instantiates the idea the priming effects for the single and dual tasks were different.

Finally, objective and subjective awareness criteria during the prime visibility block as well as subjective visibility judgments between the dual-task priming and the prime visibility blocks was compared by transforming both measures to a common sensitivity measure (d') following and adapting the procedure depicted by Szczepanowski and Pessoa (2007). In this method, sensitivity for the offline (objective) measure of prime visibility (e.g., d'_{obj}) was calculated for each participant by treating one level (e.g., square probes) as the signal and the other level (e.g., diamond probes) as noise during the 2AFC discrimination task. d' for the online (subjective) measure (d'_{subj}) was calculated by assuming that trials in which the prime was presented and participants indicated being aware of it (PAS = 2, 3 and 4) corresponded to “Hits”, whereas trials in which the prime was not present (catch trials) and participants indicated being aware of its presentation were considered “False alarms”. This allowed us to compare prime awareness estimations derived from objective (d'_{obj}) and subjective (d'_{subj}) measures within a common signal detection theory (SDT) framework, as well as to analyze possible differences between the subjective judgments given in the dual-task priming block and the prime visibility block due to the different requirements of the tasks. A Bayes Factor was computed to obtain the ratio of $P(\text{Data}|M_1)/P(\text{Data}|M_0)$, where *Model 1* was the position that the two estimations were different, and *Model 0* the position that they were the same.

3. Results

All the tests conducted below are available at the Open Science Repository, https://osf.io/stcdh/?view_only=af3fe6f2ca8941a1b894b7a83fbd2234. NHST analyses were consistent with the analyses reported below (see Supplementary Materials).

3.1. Experiment 1: Prime-mask SOA of 40 ms

Twenty participants took part in Experiment 1 (nineteen women, age range = 19-61 years, $M = 31.10$, $SD = 13.30$). The number of participants that took part in the experiment was calculated by monitoring the Bayes factor (BF) values in the regression analysis (Goldstein et al., 2022) at the end of each experimental day (see section 2.1 for a detailed explanation). One participant was excluded and replaced due to low accuracy levels (< 75% accuracy). Three participants were excluded and replaced for incorrectly using the PAS scale (e.g., > 10% “clear perception” reports for catch trials in either the dual-task priming or visibility blocks). Given that the participants’

responses were highly accurate (single-task; Congruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.15$, Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.16$; dual-task; Congruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.16$, Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.15$) only data on RTs was analyzed.

Single-task analyses

Following the classical dissociation paradigm (Reingold & Merikle, 1988), individual mean RT data was sent to a Bayesian paired sample t -test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials. The analysis showed moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.307$, error % = 0.02) against a priming effect by the global shape, showing that the obtained RTs (Congruent: $M = 581$ ms, $SE = 16.21$; Incongruent: $M = 584$ ms, $SE = 16.45$; see **Tables 2** and **4**, and **Figure 4**) were 3.256 times more likely under the null hypothesis (e.g., no differences in RT between congruent and incongruent trials).

Prime discrimination responses from the prime visibility task ($M = .61$, $SE = 0.03$) were transformed into a sensibility measure (d'_{obj} ; $M = 0.655$, $SE = 0.21$) and sent to a Bayesian one sample t -test. A BF_{10} of 7.776 (error % = 2.444×10^{-7}) provided substantial evidence against the group visibility performance being at strict chance-level (i.e., $d'_{obj}=0$).

RT data was also analyzed by implementing a Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression method (Goldstein et al., 2022; Greenwald et al., 1995). Priming scores (log-RT incongruent – congruent conditions) were predicted from centered awareness scores (see footnote 5), with the regression intercept representing the predicted effect for a given participant whose awareness level in the objective task is at chance level. Results showed strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.096$, C.I -0.0034/0.018) against a priming effect by the global shape, indicating that the data was 10.42 times more likely under the null model where the intercept is set to 0 (no subliminal priming effect) compared to a model drawn from a wide normal distribution (see **Figure 5**).

Experiment	Task	RT			
		Congruent		Incongruent	
		M	SE	M	SE
	Single				
40 ms		581	16.2	584	16.5
53 ms		539	17.5	555	16.7
67 ms		508	11.5	521	10.9
Unmasked		524	17.7	554	17.3
	Dual PAS1				
40 ms		794	47.2	791	49.1
53 ms		769	41.9	773	40.7
67 ms		663	28.7	665	27.9
Unmasked		768	40.2	791	40.6
	Dual				
40 ms		814	51.6	808	53.4
53 ms		780	41.3	778	38.5
67 ms		682	34.6	679	32.4
Unmasked		801	46.6	817	45.9

Table 2. Mean (M) and standard error (SE) for RTs (ms) in congruent and incongruent conditions in the single-task priming block, dual-task priming block (filtered by PAS1), and the dual-task priming block (unfiltered) across all four experiments.

PAS	Experiment							
	40 ms		53 ms		67 ms		Unmasked	
	M	SE	M	SE	M	SE	M	SE
	Dual-task							
1	82	23.9	75	26.9	60	28.6	56	26.6
2	11	11.0	20	21.3	31	21.4	27	16.9
3	3	5.1	4	6.4	8	8.9	12	11.9
4	5	14.5	1	2.1	1	2.2	6	10.1
	Prime Visibility							
1	61	33.1	53	37.4	36	33.2	16	28.7
2	20	16.1	23	21.5	36	22.9	11	17.3
3	12	13.3	17	21.8	21	20.4	23	24.0
4	7	16.0	8	12.3	7	13.1	49	38.2

Table 3. Mean (M) and standard error (SE) for PAS reports (%) in the dual-task priming block and the prime visibility block across all four experiments.

Figure 4. Priming effects (Incongruent – Congruent) in both the single-task priming block, the dual-task priming block (filtered by PAS1), and the dual-task priming block (unfiltered). Error bars represent standard error (SE) of the mean.

Figure 5. Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression in Experiment 1 (SOA 40). (A) Histogram of the posterior estimation of the intercept (in log RT units). (B) Credible interval (2.5, 97.5) for the estimation of the intercept. The red line bounds the interval limits, and the green point indicates an intercept value of 0. (C) Depiction of the corrected Greenwald regression. Each circle represents a participant's estimated true score. The x-axis represents the centered awareness score, the y-axis represents the estimated effect (log-RT incongruent – congruent conditions). The intercept is the expected performance for completely unaware participants.

Dual-task analyses

In the dual-task priming block, the distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 (no perception of the prime) was reported on 82% of the trials, PAS2 (weak perception) on 11% of the

trials, PAS3 (almost clear perception) on 3% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 5% of the trials (see **Table 3** and **Figure 5**).

RT data from the dual-task priming block was planned to be sent to a 2 x 4 repeated measures Bayesian ANOVA with Congruency (Congruent vs. Incongruent) and PAS (1: No perception; 2: Weak perception; 3: Almost clear perception, and 4: Clear perception) as factors. However, PAS3 and PAS4 were marginally used in Experiment 1: only 8 participants used PAS3 reports, and PAS4 reports were used by 5 participants. When reporting PAS3, only 2 participants had more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions, whereas when reporting PAS4, only 3 participants had more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions⁷. Hence, considering (i) the small datasets for PAS3 and PAS4, (ii) that only a marginal number of participants would enter the Bayesian ANOVA after listwise deletion of participants with missing values, (iii) and the fact that the main focus of the present study was exploring the integration of local elements into global shape in the absence of awareness, individual mean RT data for PAS1 reports (trials with no subjective awareness of the primes) was sent to a Bayesian paired sample *t*-test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials. The analysis showed moderate evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.278$, error % = 0.019) against a congruency effect by the global shape in the dual-task priming block (PAS1-Congruent: $M = 794$ ms, $SE = 47.18$; PAS1-Incongruent: $M = 790$ ms, $SE = 49.11$; see **Tables 2** and **4**, and **Figure 4**).

⁷ The minimum number of trials for each condition was not specified in the Stage 1 of the pre-registered proposal. However, a minimum number of trials per condition is necessary to get robust individual mean RT data that can enter statistical analyses. We considered this minimum to be 10 trials at each condition, while other recent studies have been more restrictive using a 20 trials minimum cut-off (e.g., Kiefer et al., 2023).

Figure 6. PAS distributions. A) PAS reports (%) in the dual-task priming block; B) PAS reports (%) in the Prime Visibility task. Error bars represent standard error (SE) of the mean.

RT: Single-task vs. dual-task comparison.

To test the hypothesis that RTs increase during the dual-task priming block compared to the single-task priming block, individual mean RTs from the two different priming blocks were sent to a 2 x 2 Bayesian repeated-measures ANOVA with Block (single-task, dual-task) and Congruency (congruent, incongruent) as within-subjects factors. Model comparison showed that a model with only Task as a main factor explained the data 3.4 times better than a model with Task and

Congruency as main factors (Task: $BF = 55.200$, error % = 3.810; Task and Congruency: $BF = 16.228$, error % = 2.837; both against the null model without factors). Averaging the conclusions from each candidate model weighted by that model's posterior plausibility (i.e., Bayesian Model Averaging) showed strong evidence in favor of task differences on RTs (Task: $BF_{incl} = 53.965$). The analysis also showed substantial evidence against a congruency effect (Congruency: $BF_{incl} = 0.295$), in line with the fact that in neither of the two tasks priming effects were found (single-task: Congruent: $M = 581$ ms, Incongruent: $M = 584$ ms; dual-task: Congruent: $M = 814$ ms, Incongruent: $M = 808$ ms; see **Table 2** and **Figure 4**). Anecdotal evidence for a Task and Congruency interaction (Task x Congruency: $BF_{incl} = 0.681$) suggested no response facilitation differences between the tasks.

Visibility distributions: Dual-task vs. prime visibility block.

In the prime visibility block, the mean distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 was reported on 61% of the trials, PAS2 on 20% of the trials, PAS3 on 12% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 7% of the trials (see **Table 3** and **Figure 5**). Thus, differences in the PAS distributions between the dual-task priming block and the prime visibility block were evident and will be discussed in more detail in the General Discussion.

3.2. Experiment 2: Prime-mask SOA of 53 ms

Twenty participants took part in Experiment 2 (thirteen women, age range = 18-59 years, $M = 38.00$, $SD = 14.63$). Nine participants were excluded and replaced for incorrectly using the PAS scale (e.g., > 10% "clear perception" reports for catch trials in either the dual-task priming or visibility blocks). Given that the participants' responses were highly accurate (single-task; Congruent: $M = .99$, $SD = 0.09$, Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.13$; dual-task; Congruent: $M = .98$, $SD = 0.12$, Incongruent: $M = .98$, $SD = 0.12$) only data on RTs was analyzed.

Single-task analyses

Mean RT data was sent to a Bayesian paired sample t -test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials. The analysis showed very strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 1,476.601$, error % = 1.525×10^{-8}) in favor of a priming effect by the global shape (Congruent: $M = 539$ ms, $SE = 17.52$; Incongruent: $M = 555$ ms, $SE = 16.73$; see **Tables 2** and **4**, and **Figure 4**) for a masked SOA presentation of 53 ms.

Prime discrimination responses from the prime visibility task ($M = .63$, $SE = 0.04$) were transformed into a sensibility measure (d'_{obj} ; $M = 0.831$, $SE = 0.25$) and sent to a Bayesian one sample t -test. A BF_{10} of 12.039 (error % = 2.250×10^{-7}) provided strong evidence against the group visibility being at strict chance-level (i.e., $d'_{obj}=0$).

RT data was analyzed by implementing the Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression method (Goldstein et al., 2022; Greenwald et al., 1995), which allowed us to understand whether the priming effects found in the single-task priming block in Experiment 2 were due to a small number of participants perceiving the prime above chance levels. Results showed strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 10.12$, C.I 0.012 / 0.044) in favor of a priming effect by the global shape, indicating that the data was 10.12 times more likely under the alternative hypothesis where the intercept is drawn from a wide normal distribution (indicating a subliminal priming effect) compared to a model where the intercept is set to 0 (no priming effect) (see **Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression in Experiment 2 (SOA 53). (A) Histogram of the posterior estimation of the intercept (in log RT units). (B) Credible interval (2.5, 97.5) for the estimation of the intercept. The red line bounds the interval limits, and the green point indicates an intercept value of 0. (C) Depiction of the corrected Greenwald regression. Each circle represents the participant estimated true score. The x-axis represents the centered awareness score, the y-axis represents the estimated effect (log-RT incongruent – congruent conditions). The intercept is the expected performance for completely unaware participants.

Dual-task analyses

In the dual-task priming block, the mean distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 (no perception of the prime) was reported on 75% of the trials, PAS2 (weak perception) on 20% of the trials, PAS3 (almost clear perception) on 4% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 1% of the trials (see **Table 3** and **Figure 5**).

As discussed in section 3.1., RT data from the dual-task priming block was planned to be sent to a 2 x 4 repeated measures Bayesian ANOVA with Congruency (Congruent vs. Incongruent) and PAS (1: No perception; 2: Weak perception; 3: Almost clear perception, and 4: Clear perception) as factors. However, PAS3 and PAS4 were marginally used also in Experiment 2: only 11 participants used PAS3 reports, and PAS4 reports were used only by 5 participants. When reporting PAS3, only 5 participants had more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions, whereas when reporting PAS4, none of the participants had more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions. Hence, individual mean RT data for PAS1 reports (trials with no subjective awareness of the primes) was sent to a Bayesian paired sample *t*-test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials to assess whether the integration of local elements into global shape occurred in the absence of awareness. The analysis showed substantial evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.269$, error % = 0.019) against a congruency effect in the dual-task priming block (PAS1-Congruent: $M = 769$ ms, $SE = 41.88$; PAS1-Incongruent: $M = 773$ ms, $SE = 40.74$; see **Tables 2** and **4**, and **Figure 4**) when the masked primes were presented for 53 ms.

RT: Single-task vs. dual-task comparison

Individual mean RTs from the two different priming blocks were sent to a 2 x 2 Bayesian repeated-measures ANOVA with Block (single-task, dual-task) and Congruency (congruent, incongruent) as within-subjects factors. Model comparison showed that a model with Task + Congruency + Task*Congruency explained the data best ($BF = 10,140.650$, error % = 3.137; against the null model without factors). Averaging the conclusions from each candidate model weighted by that model's posterior plausibility (i.e., Bayesian Model Averaging) provided very strong evidence in favor of RT differences between the tasks (Task: $BF_{incl} = 1,520.685$), and in addition, substantial evidence in favor of a Task and Congruency interaction ($BF_{incl} = 8.507$). This interaction reflects the strong evidence for priming effects found in one task (e.g., the single-task; Congruent: $M = 539$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 555$ ms) and the absence of evidence for priming effects found in the other task (e.g., the dual-task; Congruent: $M = 780$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 778$ ms; see **Table 2** and **Figure 4**). The evidence against an overall Congruency effect was anecdotal ($BF_{incl} = 0.681$).

Visibility distributions: Dual-task vs. Prime Visibility block.

In the prime visibility block, the mean distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 was reported on 53% of the trials, PAS2 on 23% of the trials, PAS3 on 17% of the trials, and PAS4

(clear perception) on 8% of the trials (see **Table 3** and **Figure 5**). As in Experiment 1, differences in the PAS distributions between the dual-task priming block and the prime visibility block were also evident in Experiment 2 and will be discussed in more detail in the General Discussion.

3.3. Experiment 3: Prime-mask SOA of 67 ms

Twenty participants took part in Experiment 3 (sixteen women, age range = 19-57 years, $M = 30.00$, $SD = 12.58$). The number of participants that took part in the experiment was calculated by monitoring the Bayes factor (BF) values in the regression analysis (Goldstein et al., 2022) at the end of each experimental day (see section 2.1 for a detailed explanation). Five participants were excluded and replaced for incorrectly using the PAS scale (e.g., > 10% “clear perception” reports for catch trials in either the dual-task priming or visibility blocks). Given that the participants’ responses were highly accurate (single-task; Congruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.14$, Incongruent: $M = .96$, $SD = 0.16$; dual-task; Congruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.16$, Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.16$) only data on RTs was analyzed.

Single-task analyses

Mean RT data was sent to a Bayesian paired sample t -test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials. The analysis showed very strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 3,476.463$, error % = 2.118×10^{-9}) in favor of a priming effect by the global shape (Congruent: $M = 508$ ms, $SE = 11.50$; Incongruent: $M = 521$ ms, $SE = 10.91$; see **Tables 2** and **4**, and **Figure 4**) when the masked primes were presented for 67 ms.

Prime discrimination responses from the prime visibility task ($M = .59$, $SE = 0.03$) were transformed into a sensibility measure (d'_{obj} ; $M = 0.609$, $SE = 0.24$) and sent to a Bayesian one sample t -test. A BF_{10} of 3.113 (error % = 6.065×10^{-7}) provided substantial evidence against the group visibility performance being at strict chance-level (i.e., $d'_{obj}=0$).

RT data was analyzed by implementing the Bayesian generative modelling correction to the Greenwald regression method (Goldstein et al., 2022; Greenwald et al., 1995), to understand whether the priming effects found in the single-task priming block in Experiment 3 were due to a small number of participants perceiving the prime above chance level. Results showed strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 16.32$, C.I 0.009 / 0.032) in favor of a priming effect by the global shape, indicating that the data was 16.32 times more likely under the alternative hypothesis where the

intercept is drawn from a wide normal distribution (indicating a subliminal priming effect) compared to a model where the intercept is set to 0 (no priming effect) (see **Figure 8**).

Figure 8. Bayesian correction to Greenwald regression in Experiment 3 (SOA 67). (A) Histogram of the posterior estimation of the intercept (in log RT units). (B) Credible interval (2.5, 97.5) for the estimation of the intercept. The red line bounds the interval limits, and the green point indicates an intercept value of 0. (C) Depiction of the corrected Greenwald regression. Each circle represents the participant estimated true score. The x-axis represents the centered awareness score, the y-axis represents the estimated effect (log-RT incongruent – congruent conditions). The intercept is the expected performance for completely unaware participants.

Dual-task analyses

In the dual-task priming block, the mean distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 (no perception of the prime) was reported on 60% of the trials, PAS2 (weak perception) on 31% of the trials, PAS3 (almost clear perception) on 8% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 1% of the trials (see **Table 3** and **Figure 5**).

As discussed in Experiment 1 and 2, RT data from the dual-task priming block was planned to be sent to a 2 x 4 repeated measures Bayesian ANOVA with Congruency (Congruent vs. Incongruent) and PAS (1: No perception; 2: Weak perception; 3: Almost clear perception, and 4: Clear perception) as factors. However, PAS3 and PAS4 were marginally used also in Experiment 3: even though 15 participants used PAS3 reports, only 7 participants had more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions. PAS4 reports were used by 7 participants, none of them had more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions. Hence, individual mean RT data for PAS1 reports (trials with no subjective awareness of the primes) was sent to a Bayesian paired sample *t*-test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials to assess whether the integration of local elements into global shape occurred in the absence of awareness. The analysis showed substantial evidence ($BF_{10} = 0.317$, error % = 0.020) against a congruency effect in the dual-task priming block (PAS1-Congruent: $M = 663$ ms, $SE = 28.65$; PAS1-Incongruent: $M = 665$ ms, $SE = 27.89$; see **Tables 2** and **4**, and **Figure 4**) when the masked primes were presented for 67 ms.

RT: Single-task vs. dual-task comparison

Individual mean RTs from the two different priming blocks were sent to a 2 x 2 Bayesian repeated-measures ANOVA with Block (single-task, dual-task) and Congruency (congruent, incongruent) as within-subjects factors. Model comparison showed that a model with Task + Congruency + Task*Congruency explained the data best ($BF = 858.666$, error % = 3.824; against the null model without factors). Averaging the conclusions from each candidate model weighted by that model's posterior plausibility (i.e., Bayesian Model Averaging) provided very strong evidence in favor of RT differences between the tasks (Task: $BF_{incl} = 109.576$), and very strong evidence in favor of a Task*Congruency interaction ($BF_{incl} = 13.005$). This interaction reflects the strong evidence for priming effects found in one task (e.g., the single-task; Congruent: $M = 508$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 521$ ms) and the absence of evidence for priming effects found in the other task (e.g., the dual-

task; Congruent: $M = 682$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 679$ ms). The evidence against an overall Congruency effect was anecdotal ($BF_{incl} = 0.600$).

Visibility distributions: Dual-task vs. Prime Visibility block.

In the prime visibility block, the mean distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 was reported on 36% of the trials, PAS2 on 36% of the trials, PAS3 on 21% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 7% of the trials (see **Table 3** and **Figure 5**). Differences in the PAS distributions between the dual-task priming block and the prime visibility block were also evident in Experiment 3 and will be discussed in more detail in the General Discussion.

3.4. Experiment 4: Unmasked primes

Twenty participants took part in Experiment 4 (nineteen women, age range = 19-54 years, $M = 25.65$, $SD = 9.01$). Seven participants were excluded and replaced for incorrectly using the PAS scale (e.g., > 10% “clear perception” reports for catch trials in either the dual-task priming or visibility blocks). Given that the participants’ responses were highly accurate (single-task; Congruent: $M = .99$, $SD = 0.09$, Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.13$; dual-task; Congruent: $M = .98$, $SD = 0.13$, Incongruent: $M = .97$, $SD = 0.17$) only data on RTs was analyzed.

Single-task analyses

Mean RT data was sent to a Bayesian paired sample t -test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials. The analysis showed very strong evidence ($BF_{10} = 38,985.792$, error % = 2.296×10^{-8}) in favor of a priming effect by the global shape (Congruent: $M = 524$ ms, $SE = 17.72$; Incongruent: $M = 554$ ms, $SE = 17.31$; see **Tables 2** and **4**, and **Figure 4**) when the primes were presented unmasked.

Prime discrimination responses from the prime visibility task ($M = .91$, $SE = 0.03$) were transformed into a sensibility measure (d'_{obj} ; $M = 3.552$, $SE = 0.63$; see **Table 3**) and sent to a Bayesian one sample t -test. A BF_{10} of $1.596 \times 10^{+6}$ (error % = 5.548×10^{-9}) provided very strong evidence in favor of the above-chance visibility of the primes.

Dual-task analyses

In the dual-task priming block, the mean distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 (no perception of the prime) was reported on 56% of the trials, PAS2 (weak perception) on 27% of the

trials, PAS3 (almost clear perception) on 12% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 6% of the trials (see **Table 3** and **Figure 5**).

PAS3 and PAS4 was only marginally used in Experiment 4: even though 16 participants used PAS3 reports, only 10 participants had more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions. PAS4 reports were used by 11 participants, but only 4 of them had more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions. Therefore, individual mean RT data for PAS1 reports (no perception of the primes) was sent to a Bayesian paired sample t -test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials to assess whether priming effects were found when the primes were presented unmasked but participants reported not perceiving them (e.g., PAS1). The analysis showed anecdotal evidence ($BF_{10} = 2.798$, error % = 7.857×10^{-7}) in favor of a priming effect by the global shape (PAS1-Congruent: $M = 768$ ms, $SE = 40.16$; PAS1-Incongruent: $M = 791$ ms, $SE = 40.55$; see **Tables 2** and **4**, and **Figure 4**). Note that NHST paired t -tests suggest a significant priming effect when the primes were unmasked but participants reported no perception of the primes (see Supplementary Materials).

RT: Single-task vs. dual-task comparison.

Individual mean RTs from the two different priming blocks were sent to a 2 x 2 Bayesian repeated-measures ANOVA with Block (single-task, dual-task) and Congruency (congruent, incongruent) as within-subjects factors. Model comparison showed that a model with Task + Congruency + Task*Congruency explained the data best ($BF = 6.262 \times 10^{+6}$, error % = 4.862; against the null model without factors). Averaging the conclusions from each candidate model weighted by that model's posterior plausibility (i.e., Bayesian Model Averaging) provided very strong evidence in favor of RT differences between the tasks (Task: $BF_{incl} = 653.723$), and, in addition, very strong evidence in favor of an overall Congruency effect ($BF_{incl} = 2852.396$). Indeed, when the primes were presented unmasked, reliable priming effects were found in both the single (Congruent: $M = 524$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 554$ ms) and the dual-task (Congruent: $M = 801$ ms; Incongruent: $M = 817$ ms; see **Table 2** and **Figure 4**) priming blocks. The interaction between Task and Congruency was anecdotal ($BF_{incl} = 2.831$), providing anecdotal evidence in favor of priming effect differences between the tasks.

Visibility distributions: Dual-task vs. Prime Visibility block

In the prime visibility block, the mean distribution of PAS reports was as follows: PAS1 was reported on 16% of the trials, PAS2 on 11% of the trials, PAS3 on 23% of the trials, and PAS4 (clear perception) on 49% of the trials (see **Table 3** and **Figure 5**). Differences in the PAS distributions between the dual-task priming block and the prime visibility block were also evident when the primes were presented unmasked and will be discussed in more detail in the General Discussion.

Experiment	Task	Single-task				Dual-task	
		Priming		Regression		Priming-PAS1	
		BF ₁₀	Error	BF ₁₀	Error	BF ₁₀	Error
1. SOA 40 ms		0.307	0.020	0.096	NA	0.278	0.019
2. SOA 53 ms		1,476.601	1.525 x 10 ⁻⁸	10.120	NA	0.269	0.019
3. SOA 67 ms		3,476.463	2.118 x 10 ⁻⁹	16.320	NA	0.317	0.020
4. Unmasked		38,985.792	2.296 x 10 ⁻⁸	NA	NA	2.798	7.857 x 10 ⁻⁷

Table 4. Bayes factor (BF₁₀) and error percentage (%) of the BF₁₀ estimate for priming effects (incongruent – congruent RTs) and Bayesian regression in the single-task priming block, and priming effects for PAS1 reports in the dual-task priming block.

3.5. Prime visibility task: d'_{obj} vs. d'_{subj} comparison

Objective and subjective awareness criteria were transformed into a common sensitivity measure (d') to compare prime awareness estimations derived from objective offline (2AFC) and subjective online (PAS) tasks along the four experiments. Individual mean d' s during the dual task (d'_{subj}) and visibility blocks (d'_{obj} vs. d'_{subj}) were sent to Bayesian paired sample t -tests to assess (1) whether prime awareness estimations differed between objective and subjective measures during the same block (visibility block), and (2) whether prime awareness estimations differed between the dual-task block and the visibility block. Regarding the comparisons between d'_{obj} and d'_{subj} within the visibility block, all t -tests showed only anecdotal evidence in favor or against the position that the two estimations were different, except for the comparison between d'_{obj} and d'_{subj} in the SOA40 experiment, which yielded substantial evidence against the position that the two estimations were different (see **Table 5**). The comparisons between sensitivity measures between the dual-task and visibility blocks showed substantial evidence favoring the existence of

differences between d'_{obj} and d'_{subj} in the SOA 53 condition, strong evidence favoring the existence of differences between both d'_{subjs} in the SOA 67 condition, and very strong evidence favoring the existence of differences between d'_{obj} and d'_{subj} , and between both d'_{subjs} measures in the unmasked condition (see **Table 5** for a summary of the comparisons between sensitivity measures). These results seem to be driven by an overall increased visibility of the primes during the visibility block, compared to the dual-task priming block (see **Figure 9**).

Experiment	d' (c)	Comparison	BF ₁₀	error %
1. SOA 40 ms	$d'_{obj(visibility)} = .655 (-0,238)$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	0.240	0.018
	$d'_{subj(visibility)} = .626 (0,859)$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(dual-task)}$	1.116	0.024
	$d'_{subj(dual-task)} = .226 (1,363)$	$d'_{subj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(dual-task)}$	1.659	2.205×10^{-6}
2. SOA 53 ms	$d'_{obj(visibility)} = .831 (-0,213)$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	0.620	0.023
	$d'_{subj(visibility)} = .547 (0,557)$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(dual-task)}$	6.380	2.550×10^{-7}
	$d'_{subj(dual-task)} = .092 (1,046)$	$d'_{subj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(dual-task)}$	1.287	0.023
3. SOA 67 ms	$d'_{obj(visibility)} = .609 (-0,248)$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	0.496	0.023
	$d'_{subj(visibility)} = .837 (-0,029)$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(dual-task)}$	1.437	2.729×10^{-6}
	$d'_{subj(dual-task)} = .081 (0,431)$	$d'_{subj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(dual-task)}$	11.852	2.235×10^{-7}
4. Unmasked	$d'_{obj(visibility)} = 3.552 (-0,044)$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(visibility)}$	2.400	1.109×10^{-6}
	$d'_{subj(visibility)} = 3.136 (0,023)$	$d'_{obj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(dual-task)}$	225625.220	2.739×10^{-11}
	$d'_{subj(dual-task)} = .791 (0,683)$	$d'_{subj(visibility)} - d'_{subj(dual-task)}$	22447.750	2.544×10^{-8}

Table 5. Sensitivity (d') and response bias (c), Bayes factor (BF₁₀), and error (%) for the comparisons between d'_{obj} and d'_{subj} sensitivity measures across all four experiments.

Additionally, the computation of response bias (c) for both the objective and subjective awareness measures produced some interesting results. Positive values of c in the dual-task priming block across experiments suggest that participants used the PAS scale rather conservatively (e.g., a preference for “PAS1: no perception” reports), in line with the interpretation that participants’ focus was directed to the main probe discrimination task in this block. In the prime visibility block, participants showed a slight preference for reporting “no signal” (e.g., PAS1: no perception) when

subjectively assessing prime visibility, and a very small preference for reporting “signal” when prime visibility was assessed objectively through the 2AFC prime discrimination task (note that in this case, “square” response was mapped as “signal”, whereas “diamond” response was associated with “no signal”, independent of prime identity). Interestingly, response preferences in both the objective or subjective awareness measures seem to converge for increasing visibility of the primes (e.g., SOA 67 ms and unmasked condition).

Figure 9. Sensitivity measures (d') obtained during the dual task (d'_{subj}) and visibility blocks (d'_{obj} and d'_{subj}).

4. Discussion

In the present study, we used a masked priming design with non-hierarchical visual arrays presented in four different masking conditions to explore whether local elements group into global shape in the absence of awareness. Two different masked priming designs (e.g., the classic dissociation paradigm and a trial-by-trial probe and prime discrimination task) were introduced to explore whether the introduction of an online visibility measure influenced the facilitation (congruency) effect of the primes, and participant's awareness was measured using both objective and subjective measures of awareness. Crucially, retinotopic effects were controlled by introducing different size prime and probe stimuli. Our results suggest that local elements group into global shape in the absence of awareness, both prime-mask SOA and the masked priming design (single vs. dual-task) being crucial factors in the processing of the global shape without awareness⁸.

Following the classic dissociation paradigm (Reingold & Merikle, 1988), we aimed to show differences between a performance measure (congruency effects from the single-task priming block) and an awareness measure on the same stimuli (d'_{obj} calculated from participants' performance in the prime visibility block). In the single-task priming block, reliable priming effects were found for a prime-mask SOA of 53 ms (Experiment 2) and 67 ms (Experiment 3), but not for the shorter SOA of 40 ms (Experiment 1, see **Figure 4** and **Tables 2** and **4**). As discussed earlier, two common challenges of the dissociation paradigm refer to the objective, performance based, measure of awareness that it is assessed in a separate block than the priming task. One of the challenges is that aggregated awareness (e.g., mean awareness level of the whole sample) might not be at strict chance level (Rouder et al., 2007). In line with this objection, we found that mean group awareness levels for the masked experiments were in all cases above strict chance-level (mean group accuracy ranged from .59 to .63, and d'_{obj} values between 0.609 and 0.831). To avoid any post hoc data selection (with potential *regression to the mean* effects; Rothkirch et al., 2022; Shanks, 2017), but to rule out that the priming effects found in Exp. 2 and 3 were due to a small number of participants consciously perceiving the primes, we implemented the Bayesian generative model recently proposed by Goldstein et al. (2022). This method allows to estimate the intercept in a regression model, which represents the predicted effect for a given participant whose

⁸ As one reviewer noted, the fact that most participants were females might have some consequences for the generalizability of the results. This possibility should be tested in forthcoming studies.

awareness level in the objective task is at chance level while accounting for the error in the awareness and effect measurements. In other words, Goldstein's Bayesian generative model provides an unbiased estimate of the actual unconscious effect⁹. Using this method, we obtained strong evidence in favor of an unconscious priming effect both in Experiment 2 (SOA of 53 ms) and Experiment 3 (SOA of 67 ms), but not in Experiment 1 (SOA of 40), where the analysis showed substantial evidence for the null hypothesis (see **Table 4**).

The second objection to the dissociation paradigm is based on the fact that, since the visibility of the prime is not assessed on a trial-by-trial basis but rather in a different experimental block, the prime could be (minimally) visible in some (or many) trials during the priming task (e.g., an underestimation of prime visibility in the priming task). The implementation of objective (offline) and subjective (online) visibility measures in both the same and different blocks allowed us to convert both to a common sensitivity measure (d') and compare their respective awareness estimations (Szczepanowski & Pessoa, 2007; Lähteenmäki et al., 2015). The distribution of PAS reports between the two tasks (see **Figure 5**) showed that low or no visibility reports (e.g., PAS1 or PAS2) were significantly more frequently used when participants perform the dual-task priming block, compared to the prime visibility block. This was confirmed by the fact that subjective sensitivity measures of awareness (d'_{subj}) collected during the dual-task block were consistently lower compared to those of the visibility block. Thus, accessing prime information seems to be easier, and hence the awareness of the primes higher, when participant's attention is exclusively focused on the prime display as happens in the prime visibility block. In the single-task priming block, on the other hand, participants' focus of attention is fully directed to the probe discrimination task and no attention needs to be deployed to the primes, thus visibility of the primes is most presumably lower than the one inferred from the prime visibility block. Note that, apart from attentional factors, different strategies might be implemented by participants in the prime

⁹ Note that the intercept is the predicted effect when the awareness score is 0 (the unconscious effect), which is independent of the positive correlation between the effect and the awareness level. However, in the method originally proposed by Greenwald et al. (1995), the intercept was a biased estimate of the actual nonconscious effect, due to the underestimation of the regression slope and the resulting overestimation of the intercept (regression attenuation/dilution). This bias is what the Bayesian generative model approach developed by Goldstein et al. (2022) avoids. Nonetheless, one might argue that conscious perception explains the regression results very well, given the apparently positive slope, with possibly a small unconscious perception effect. Against this alternative interpretation, the regression coefficients for each of the experiments indicates that none of them is statistically different from 0 (SOA40: $r = .135$, $p = .572$; SOA53: $r = .119$, $p = .616$; SOA63: $r = .409$, $p = .073$).

visibility block. One such strategy consists of focusing on a specific area of the display, and inferring from the brief perception of a corner in that area whether the prime was a square or a diamond, a strategy that participants informally discussed after completing the task. In addition, the trial sequence between the single-task priming block and the prime visibility block was slightly different in the present study: whereas in the priming block the probe followed the mask, in the prime visibility block an alternative 2AFC choice display followed the mask (see **Figure 2**). The 2AFC display in the prime visibility block might have reduced the masking effect compared to the central presentation of the probe in the priming block. Overall, the argument seems to unfold in the opposite direction to the objection to objective measures pointed out above: the visibility of the prime in the single-task priming block might be lower than the visibility of the prime inferred from the prime visibility block, or in other words, the dissociation paradigm might be overestimating actual prime perception.

Overall, results from the Bayesian regression model as well as the response facilitation observed in the single-task priming block provide strong evidence in favor of the hypothesis that local elements group into a global shape in the absence of awareness. This reinforces the importance of implementing new approaches (see Tsikandilakis et al., 2023, for an alternative Bayesian method that determines unbiased individual unaware thresholds) in the study of unconscious priming. Previous mixed results on global shape perception from local elements might be related to different experimental decisions, such as prime duration condition (e.g., presenting the prime too briefly; Sabary et al., 2020), the introduction of hierarchical primes (e.g., presenting local elements that might interfere with the processing of the global shape; Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2004; Sabary et al., 2020), the method to render the stimulus invisible (e.g., using suppression techniques, which seem to disrupt stimulus information at very early stages of visual processing; Schwarzkopf & Rees, 2011) or the introduction of online measures of awareness within the priming block (e.g., the trial-by-trial report of subjective prime visibility, which weakens prime-related activation and stimulus-response links; Sabary et al., 2020). Therefore, our results are in agreement with previous studies suggesting organization of elements into a global shape in the absence of visual awareness (Jimenez et al., 2017, 2018; Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2004) and, from a broader perspective, with those studies supporting the subliminal processing of Gestalt grouping cues (Devyatko et al., 2019; Kimchi et al., 2018; Montoro et al., 2014). Taken together, all of these findings suggest that, even when visual processing is severely impaired or weakened, perceptual organizational operations

can effectively structure visual scene information. This evidence in favor of multiple Gestalt operations occurring subliminally seems to pose a challenge to those explanations that equate grouping processes and/or feature integration with consciousness (Lamme, 2015), and they expand further the limits of unconscious visual processing within the visual system.

From a neurophysiological point of view, masking is considered to play a role in re-entrant processing of stimulus information (Boehler et al., 2008; Liu et al., 2009), yet it is also argued that early pattern mask reduces the bottom-up signal from the primes leading to a weaker feedforward sweep, or the mask may follow the initial feedforward sweep which contains prime information increasing the feature noise within the information processing (see Enns & Di Lollo, 2000, for a review). A feasible conclusion from the present and previous studies (e.g., Jimenez et al., 2017) is that that interrupting the visual processing of the stimulus earlier than 50 ms (e.g., by introducing noise through a pattern mask) critically interferes with the visual system's ability to construct a global shape from local elements, yet masking the primes after 50 ms does not seem to prevent the grouping of the local elements into a global shape. Future studies exploring the brain basis and specific time course of global shape perception would likely produce interesting insights in the neural mechanisms behind this observation.

Interestingly, when participants performed the dual-task priming block, no priming effects were found for the masked prime presentations in neither Exp. 1, 2 or 3. For unmasked primes (Experiment 4), both the single and dual-tasks produced significant priming effects yet of lower magnitude in the dual-task. Priming results from the dual-task priming block suggest that the introduction of a trial-by-trial online visibility measure weakens prime-related activation and stimulus-response links between prime and probe (e.g., Ansorge et al., 2010; Avneon & Lamy, 2018; Kinoshita & Hunt, 2008; even though some studies do obtain priming effects, these are agreeably smaller than in prime only trials, e.g., Biafora & Schdmit, 2022; Haase & Fisk, 2015). Similarly, a recent study by Kiefer et al. (2023) compared masked semantic priming effects assessed using both the classical sequential procedure (e.g., following the dissociation logic) and a condition in which prime awareness was rated within the priming experiment (e.g., trials-wise using the PAS). In line with the results reported here, their results revealed general priming effects only in the PAS-absent group. The authors concluded that assessing subjective perceptual experience on a trial-by-trial basis heavily interfered with semantic processes underlying masked priming, presumably due to attentional demands associated with concurrent prime identification.

This seems to be the case not only in semantic priming, but also in response priming processes as suggested by the results reported here. As discussed by Kiefer et al. (2023), the introduction of a trial-by-trial measure of awareness seems to reduce the attentional resources necessary for the operation of priming-related processes and therefore induce interference with the primed decision. To avoid criterion confounds in the use of the PAS scale in the dual-task priming block (e.g., criterion shifts from reporting the perception of the local elements or the global shape of the primes), participants were carefully instructed to report their subjective experience of the global shape while avoiding any report on their subjective visibility of the local elements. We speculated that possible response facilitation effects in the dual-task priming block might be confounded if what participants' subjective reports referred to (e.g., perception of the local elements as opposed to perception of the global shape) was not clear. In other words, participants' visibility reports based on the (marginal) perception of an individual local element without being aware of the global shape of the prime per se could influence the reliability of subsequent priming effects in previous studies. However, we found that this manipulation did not have any influence on the observed response facilitations in the dual-task priming block. Therefore, the main factor behind the absence of priming effects in the dual-task priming block seem to be the introduction of online visibility ratings on the masked primes.

It might be argued that the instructions to the participants in the present study created a conservative bias as shown by the high percentage of PAS1 ratings relative to other categories. Indeed, even though both measures of awareness (e.g., d'_{obj} and d'_{subj}) provide similar estimates of awareness (see **Figure 9**) as measured in the prime visibility block, participants showed a small preference for reporting “no signal” when using the PAS scale (see criterion (c) in **Table 5**). The exploration of the effects of PAS instructions (by introducing more liberal scale categories, e.g., PAS2: ‘Perceived some part of the figure that suggests it was a square or diamond’) in the context of masked priming is an interesting topic for future research. Overall, we would like to stress the challenges in implementing the PAS scale in masked priming studies and consciousness research in general (Biafora & Schmidt, 2022). As used in many studies, the PAS inquires somewhat vaguely about participant's awareness of a stimulus, granting the participant full responsibility to map the different category points into subjective perceptual meaning. If the intention is to produce meaningful and comparable results, the PAS should not be applied as it is, but combined with a clear instruction to which aspect of subjective experience is to be rated.

One of the crucial challenges for the dissociation paradigm, and for consciousness research more broadly, refers to the adequacy of a method for measuring conscious processing, and whether objective or subjective measures are equivalent for this purpose (Merikle et al., 2001; Persuh, 2018). In fact, while objective procedures consist of interpreting indicators of perception (detection/discrimination) as indicators of conscious perception, subjective (visibility) procedures ask participants whether they saw the stimulus or not in each trial, so both measures are apparently based on and could be measuring different contents (Michel, 2023). However, our results suggest that when collected under the same conditions (as occurs in the visibility block in the present work) and converted into a common sensitivity measure (e.g., d'), both measures (e.g., d'_{obj} and d'_{subj}) provide similar estimates of awareness (see **Figure 9**). These results are in line with recent findings by Kiefer et al. (2023), who employed a similar procedure to calculate d'_{subj} . The authors did not directly compare d'_{obj} and d'_{subj} , but the reported values indicated very similar sensitivity estimates for both measures. Together, these findings suggest that both objective and subjective estimates measure equivalent or at least similar awareness dimensions or contents, and could be used interchangeably under appropriate experimental conditions, even if they do not capture exactly the same aspects of the subjects' phenomenological experience (Block, 1995, Ramsøy & Overgaard, 2004).

In sum, our results suggest that local elements group into global shape in the absence of awareness, prime-mask SOA and the masked priming design (single vs. dual-task) being crucial factors in the processing of the global shape without awareness. Assessing subjective perceptual experience of the prime on a trial-by-trial basis heavily interferes with the processes underlying masked priming, therefore future studies exploring priming effects elicited by masked stimuli should take this into serious consideration. In addition, prime presentation seems to be a crucial factor in the processing of the global shape from local elements in the absence of awareness: whereas a prime duration of 40 ms seems too restrictive for the prime related activation to produce reliable priming effects, increasing prime-mask SOA to 53 ms allows the prime to influence subsequent probe responses, a priming effect that is replicated for a prime-mask SOA of 67 ms.

One of the challenges of the dissociation paradigm refers to the problem of visibility of the prime not being assessed on a trial-by-trial basis but rather in a different experimental block, and therefore the prime could be visible in some (or many) trials during the priming task (e.g., underestimation of prime visibility in the priming task). The implementation of objective (offline)

and subjective (online) visibility measures in both the same and different blocks allowed us to confirm that subjective sensitivity measures of awareness collected during the dual-task block were consistently lower compared to those of the visibility block. Even though further research is needed, these results suggest that prime visibility in the priming task might be lower than the prime visibility inferred from the prime visibility block. A second challenge of the dissociation paradigm refers to the aggregated awareness (e.g., mean awareness level of the whole sample) not being at strict chance level (Rouder et al., 2007). The implementation of new approaches and Bayesian inference (Goldstein et al., 2022; Tsikandilakis et al., 2023) might be crucial in the future study of unconscious automatic processes.

Data Availability

The methods used and the data analyzed in the present study are available in the Open Science Framework (OSF) repository, in the following link:

https://osf.io/stcdh/?view_only=af3fe6f2ca8941a1b894b7a83fbd2234

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Professor Ruth Kimchi, Dr. Shahar Sabary and Dr. Dina Devyatko for kindly sharing the mask stimuli for this study.

Funding acknowledgment

The present project is supported by Grant PID2021-125842NB-I00 from Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Spain).

Pablo Gómez is supported by Grant SMA-2127135 from the National Science Foundation (United States).

Antonio Prieto is supported by Grant 2022V/ITEMP/007 from UNED-SANTANDER.

References

- Ansorge, U., Fuchs, I., Khalid, S., & Kunde, W. (2011). No conflict control in the absence of awareness. *Psychological Research*, *75*(5), 351–365. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-010-0313-4>
- Avneon, M., & Lamy, D. (2018). Reexamining unconscious response priming: A liminal-prime paradigm. *Consciousness and Cognition*, *59*, 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2017.12.006>
- Bachmann, T., 2015. Unmasking the pitfalls of the masking method in consciousness research. In: Overgaard, M. (Ed.), *Behavioral Methods in Consciousness Research*. Oxford University Press, Croydon, pp. 49–76.
- Behrmann, M., & Kimchi, R. (2003). What does visual agnosia tell us about perceptual organization and its relationship to object perception? *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, *29*, 19–42. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-1523.29.1.19>
- Biafora, M., & Schmidt, T. (2022). Juggling too many balls at once: Qualitatively different effects when measuring priming and masking in single, dual, and triple tasks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2208.13675*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2208.13675>
- Boehler, C. N., Schoenfeld, M. A., Heinze, H. J., & Hopf, J. M. (2008). Rapid recurrent processing gates awareness in primary visual cortex. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *105*(25), 8742–8747. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0801999105>
- Breitmeyer, B., Ogmen, H., Ramon, J., & Chen, J. (2005). Unconscious and conscious priming by forms and their parts. *Visual Cognition*, *12*(5), 720–736.
- Breitmeyer, B. G. (2015). Psychophysical “blinding” methods reveal a functional hierarchy of unconscious visual processing. *Consciousness and Cognition*, *35*, 234–250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2015.01.012>
- Brysbaert, M., & Stevens, M. (2018). Power analysis and effect size in mixed effects models: A tutorial. *Journal of Cognition*, *1*(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/joc.10>
- Chan, W. Y., & Chua, F. K. (2003). Grouping with and without attention. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, *10*(4), 932–938. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03196554>

- Chica, A. B., & Bartolomeo, P. (2012). Attentional routes to conscious perception. *Frontiers in Psychology, 3*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2012.00001>
- Cohen, M. A., Cavanagh, P., Chun, M. M., & Nakayama, K. (2012). The attentional requirements of consciousness. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 16*(8), 411-417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2012.06.013>
- Dehaene, S., & Naccache, L. (2001). Towards a cognitive neuroscience of consciousness: basic evidence and a workspace framework. *Cognition, 79*(1-2), 1-37. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277\(00\)00123-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277(00)00123-2)
- Devyatko, D., Sabary, S., & Kimchi, R. (2019). Perceptual organization of line configurations: Is visual awareness necessary? *Consciousness and Cognition, 70*, 101-115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2019.02.005>
- Dosher, B. A. (1998). The response-window regression method—Some problematic assumptions: Comment on Draine and Greenwald (1998). *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General, 127*(3), 311–317. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.127.3.311>
- Driver, J., Davis, G., Russell, C., Turatto, M., & Freeman, E. (2001). Segmentation, attention and phenomenal visual objects. *Cognition, 80*(1-2), 61-95. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277\(00\)00151-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277(00)00151-7)
- Enns, J. T., & Di Lollo, V. (2000). What's new in visual masking? *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 4*(9), 345–352. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-6613\(00\)01520-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-6613(00)01520-5)
- Eriksen, C. W. (1960). Discrimination and learning without awareness: a methodological survey and evaluation. *Psychological Review, 67*(5). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/h0041622>
- Goldstein, A., Sklar, A. Y., & Siegelman, N. (2022). Accurately measuring nonconscious processing using a generative Bayesian framework. *Psychology of Consciousness: Theory, Research, and Practice*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cns0000316>
- Greenwald, A. G., Klinger, M. R., & Schuh, E. S. (1995). Activation by marginally perceptible ("subliminal") stimuli: Dissociation of unconscious from conscious cognition. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General, 124*(1), 22–42. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.124.1.22>

- Haase, S. J., & Fisk, G. D. (2015). Awareness of “invisible” arrows in a metacontrast masking paradigm. *The American Journal of Psychology*, *128*(1), 15-30. <https://doi.org/10.5406/amerjpsyc.128.1.0015>
- Haldane, J. B. S. (1932). A note on inverse probability. *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, *28*, 55-61. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0305004100010495>
- Hoeting, J. A., Madigan, D., Raftery, & Volinsky, C. T. (1999). Bayesian model averaging: A tutorial. *Statistical Science*, *14*, 382– 417. <https://doi.org/10.1214/ss/1009212519>
- Jeffreys, H. (1998). *The theory of probability*. England: Oxford University Press.
- Jimenez, M., Grassini, S., Montoro, P. R., Luna, D., & Koivisto, M. (2018). Neural correlates of visual awareness at stimulus low vs. high-levels of processing. *Neuropsychologia*, *121*, 144–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2018.11.001>
- Jimenez, M., Hinojosa, J. A., & Montoro, P. R. (2020). Visual awareness and the levels of processing hypothesis: a critical review. *Consciousness and Cognition*, *85*, 103022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2020.103022>
- Jimenez, M., & Montoro, P. R. (2018). Illusory form perception and perceptual grouping operations under conditions of restricted visual awareness. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, *21*, E42. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sjp.2018.47>
- Jimenez, M., Montoro, P. R., & Luna, D. (2017). Global shape integration and illusory form perception in the absence of awareness. *Consciousness and Cognition*, *53*, 31-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2017.05.004>
- Jimenez, M., Poch, C., Villalba-García, C., Sabater, L., Hinojosa, J. A., Montoro, P. R., & Koivisto, M. (2021). The level of processing modulates visual awareness: evidence from behavioral and electrophysiological measures. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, *33*(7), 1295-1310. https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn_a_01712
- Jimenez, M., Villalba-Garcia, C., Luna, D., Hinojosa, J. A., & Montoro, P. R. (2019). The nature of visual awareness at stimulus energy and feature levels: A backward masking study. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, *81*(6), 1926–1943. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-019-01732-5>

- Kahneman, D., & Henik, A. (1981). *Perceptual organization and attention*. In M. Kubovy & J. R. Pomerantz (Eds.), *Perceptual organization* (pp. 181-211). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Kiefer, M., Harpaintner, M., Rohr, M., & Wentura, D. (2023). Assessing subjective prime awareness on a trial-by-trial basis interferes with masked semantic priming effects. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, *49*(2), 269. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xlm0001228>
- Kim, C-Y, & Blake, R. (2005). Psychophysical magic: rendering the visible ‘invisible’. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *9*(8), 381-388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2005.06.012>
- Kimchi, R. (1998). Uniform connectedness and grouping in the perceptual organization of hierarchical patterns. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, *24*(4), 1105-1118. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-1523.24.4.1105>
- Kimchi, R. (2000). The perceptual organization of visual objects: A microgenetic analysis. *Vision research*, *40*(10-12), 1333-1347. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0042-6989\(00\)00027-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0042-6989(00)00027-4)
- Kimchi, R., & Razpurker-Apfeld, I. (2004). Perceptual grouping and attention: Not all groupings are equal. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, *11*(4), 687-696. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03196621>
- Kimchi R (2015). The perception of hierarchical structure. Wagemans J, ed. *The Oxford Handbook of Perceptual Organization* (Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK), 129–149
- Kimchi, R., Devyatko, D., & Sabary, S. (2018). Can perceptual grouping unfold in the absence of awareness? Comparing grouping during continuous flash suppression and sandwich masking. *Consciousness and Cognition*, *60*, 37-51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2018.02.009>
- Kinoshita, S., & Hunt, L. (2008). RT distribution analysis of category congruence effects with masked primes. *Memory & Cognition*, *36*(7), 1324-1334. <https://doi.org/10.3758/MC.36.7.1324>
- Klauer, K. C., Draine, S. C., & Greenwald, A. G. (1998). An unbiased errors-in-variables approach to detecting unconscious cognition. *British Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Psychology*, *51*(2), 253-267. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8317.1998.tb00680.x>

- Koch, C., & Tsuchiya, N. (2007). Attention and consciousness: two distinct brain processes. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *11*(1), 16-22.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2006.10.012>
- Koivisto, M., & Revonsuo, A. (2004). Preconscious analysis of global structure: Evidence from masked priming. *Visual Cognition*, *11*(1), 105-127.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13506280344000266>
- Lamme, V., 2015. *The crack of dawn*. In: Metzinger, T.K., Windt, J.M. (Eds.), *Perceptual Functions and Neural Mechanisms That Mark the Transition from Unconscious Processing to Conscious Vision*. Open MIND. MIND Group, Frankfurt am Main.
<https://doi.org/10.15502/9783958570092>.
- Lamy, D., Segal, H., & Ruderman, L. (2006). Grouping does not require attention. *Perception & Psychophysics*, *68*(1), 17-31. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193652>
- Lähteenmäki, M., Hyönä, J., Koivisto, M., & Nummenmaa, L. (2015). Affective processing requires awareness. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, *144*(2), 339–365.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000040>
- Liu, H., Agam, Y., Madsen, J. R., & Kreiman, G. (2009). Timing, timing, timing: Fast decoding of object information from intracranial field potentials in human visual cortex. *Neuron*, *62*(2), 281–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2009.02.025>
- Marchetti, G. (2012). Against the view that consciousness and attention are fully dissociable. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *3*, 36. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2012.00036>
- Marr, D. (1982). *Vision: A computational investigation into the human representation and processing of visual information*. New York [etc.]: W. H. Freeman and Co.
- Matzke, D., Nieuwenhuis, S., Van Rijn, H., Slagter, H. A., Van Der Molen, M. W., & Wagenmakers, E. J. (2015). The effect of horizontal eye movements on free recall: a preregistered adversarial collaboration. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, *144*(1), <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000038>
- Merikle, P. M., Smilek, D., & Eastwood, J. D. (2001). Perception without awareness: Perspectives from cognitive psychology. *Cognition*, *79*(1-2), 115-134.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277\(00\)00126-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277(00)00126-8)

- Michel, M. (2022). How (not) to underestimate unconscious perception. *Mind & Language*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mila.12406>
- Michel, M. (2023). Confidence in consciousness research. *WIREs Cognitive Science*, 14(2), e1628. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/wcs.1628>
- Mitroff, S. R., & Scholl, B. J. (2005). Forming and updating object representations without awareness: Evidence from motion-induced blindness. *Vision Research*, 45(8), 961-967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visres.2004.09.044>
- Montoro, P. R., Luna, D., & Ortells, J. J. (2014). Subliminal Gestalt grouping: Evidence of perceptual grouping by proximity and similarity in absence of conscious perception. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 25, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2014.01.004>
- Moore, C. M., & Egeth, H. (1997). Perception without attention: evidence of grouping under conditions of inattention. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 23(2), 339. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-1523.23.2.339>
- Moors, P., Hesselmann, G., Wagemans, J., & van Ee, R. (2017). Continuous flash suppression: Stimulus fractionation rather than integration. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 21(10), 719-721. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2017.06.005>
- Morey R, & Rouder J (2022). BayesFactor: Computation of Bayes Factors for Common Designs_. R package version 0.9.12-4.4, <<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=BayesFactor>>.
- Navon, D. (1977). Forest before trees: The precedence of global features in visual perception. *Cognitive psychology*, 9(3), 353-383. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285\(77\)90012-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285(77)90012-3)
- Neisser, U. (1967). *Cognitive psychology*. New York: Appleton Century, Crofts.
- Palmer, S. E. (1999). *Vision science. Photons to phenomenology*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Persuh, M. (2018). Measuring perceptual consciousness. *Frontiers in psychology*, 8, 2320. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.02320>

- Plummer M, Best N, Cowles K, Vines K (2006). CODA: Convergence Diagnosis and Output Analysis for MCMC, *R News*, 6:7-11.
- Purcell, D. G., Stewart, A. L., & Stanovich, K. E. (1983). Another look at semantic priming without awareness. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 34, 65-71.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03205897>
- Ramsøy, T. Z., & Overgaard, M. (2004). Introspection and subliminal perception. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, 3(1), 1-23.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/B:PHEN.0000041900.30172.e8>
- Rashal, E., Yeshurun, Y., & Kimchi, R. (2017). Attentional requirements in perceptual grouping depend on the processes involved in the organization. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, 79(7), 2073-2087. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-017-1365-y>
- Reingold, E. M., & Merikle, P. M. (1988). Using direct and indirect measures to study perception without awareness. *Perception & psychophysics*, 44(6), 563-575.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03207490>
- Rothkirch, M., Shanks, D. R., & Hesselmann, G. (2022). The pervasive problem of post hoc data selection in studies on unconscious processing: A reply to Sklar, Goldstein, and Hassin (2021). *Experimental Psychology*, 69(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1618-3169/a000541>
- Rouder, J. N., Morey, R. D., Speckman, P. L., & Pratte, M. S. (2007). Detecting chance: A solution to the null sensitivity problem in subliminal priming. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 14(4), 597-605. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03196808>
- Rouder, J. N. (2014). Optional stopping: No problem for Bayesians. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, 21(2), 301-308. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-014-0595-4>
- Russell, C., & Driver, J. (2005). New indirect measures of “inattentive” visual grouping in a change-detection task. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 67(4), 606-623.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193518>
- Sand, A., & Nilsson, M. E. (2016). Subliminal or not? Comparing null-hypothesis and Bayesian methods for testing subliminal priming. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 44, 29-40.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2016.06.012>

- Sabary, S., Devyatko, D., & Kimchi, R. (2020). The role of visual awareness in processing of global structure: Evidence from the perceptual organization of hierarchical patterns. *Cognition*, 205, 104442. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2020.104442>
- Sackur, J., 2013. Two dimensions of visibility revealed by multidimensional scaling of metacontrast. *Cognition*, 126, 173–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2012.09.013>
- Schönbrodt, F. D., Wagenmakers, E. J., Zehetleitner, M., & Perugini, M. (2017). Sequential hypothesis testing with Bayes factors: Efficiently testing mean differences. *Psychological methods*, 22(2), 322. <https://doi.org/10.1037/met0000061>
- Schwarzkopf, D. S., & Rees, G. (2011). Interpreting local visual features as a global shape requires awareness. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 278(1715), 2207-2215. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2010.1909>
- Shanks, D. R., & John, M. F. S. (1994). Characteristics of dissociable human learning systems. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 17(3), 367-395. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X00035032>
- Shanks, D. R. (2017). Regressive research: The pitfalls of post hoc data selection in the study of unconscious mental processes. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 24(3), 752-775. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-016-1170-y>
- Sklar, A. Y., Goldstein, A., & Hassin, R. R. (2021). Regression to the mean does not explain away nonconscious processing: A critical review of Shanks 2017. *Experimental Psychology*, 68(3), 130–136. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1618-3169/a000518>
- Szczepanowski, R., & Pessoa, L. (2007). Fear perception: Can objective and subjective awareness measures be dissociated? *Journal of Vision*, 7(4), 10-10. <https://doi.org/10.1167/7.4.10>
- Treisman, A. (1982). Perceptual grouping and attention in visual search for features and for objects. *Journal of experimental psychology: human perception and performance*, 8(2), 194-214. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-1523.8.2.194>
- Treisman, A. (1985). Preattentive processing in vision. *Computer vision, graphics, and image processing*, 31(2), 156-177. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0734-189X\(85\)80004-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0734-189X(85)80004-9)

- Timmermans, B., & Cleeremans, A. (2015). How can we measure awareness? An overview of current methods. In M. Overgaard (Ed.), *Behavioural methods in consciousness research* (pp. 21-46). Oxford University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199688890.001.0001>
- Tsikandilakis, M., Bali, P., Karlis, A., Mével, P. A., Madan, C., Derrfuss, J., & Milbank, A. (2023). Unbiased Individual Unconsciousness: Rationale, Replication and Developing Applications. *Current Research in Behavioral Sciences*, 100109.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbeha.2023.100109>
- Tunney, R. J., & Shanks, D. R. (2003). Subjective measures of awareness and implicit cognition. *Memory & Cognition*, 31(7), 1060-1071. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03196127>
- Vandenbroucke, A. R., Sligte, I. G., Fahrenfort, J. J., Ambroziak, K. B., & Lamme, V. A. (2012). Non-attended representations are perceptual rather than unconscious in nature. *PLoS One*, 7(11), e50042. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0050042>
- van den Bergh, D., Wagenmakers, E. J., & Aust, F. (2022). Bayesian Repeated-Measures ANOVA: An Updated Methodology Implemented in JASP.
<https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/fb8zn>
- Van den Bussche, E., Vermeiren, A., Desender, K., Gevers, W., Hughes, G., Verguts, T., & Reynvoet, B. (2013). Disentangling conscious and unconscious processing: a subjective trial-based assessment approach. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 7, 769.
- Wagemans, J., Elder, J. H., Kubovy, M., Palmer, S. E., Peterson, M. A., Singh, M., & von der Heydt, R. (2012). A century of Gestalt psychology in visual perception: I. Perceptual grouping and figure-ground organization. *Psychological bulletin*, 138(6), 1172.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029333>
- Wagenmakers, E. J., Marsman, M., Jamil, T., Ly, A., Verhagen, J., Love, J., ... & Morey, R. D. (2018). Bayesian inference for psychology. Part I: Theoretical advantages and practical ramifications. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 25(1), 35-57.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-017-1343-3>